

IN FAIRY TALES MYTHICAL ELEMENTS

Haydarova Gulhayo Ahmadaliyevna

Qo'qon DPI o'qituvchi

Email: h.gulhayoxon1990@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0007-8262-304X

Sobitova Robiyaxon Salohiddin qizi

Qo'qon DPI talaba.

Email: robiyaxonsobitova0@gmail.com

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Annotation: The essence of myth being fabrication and fiction means it naturally shares a unique intrinsic connection with the fairy tale genre. Through the analysis of myth and fairy tale materials, the scope of meanings related to the mythological layer in fairy tales is unveiled. The place of mythological concepts in the interpretation of fairy tale characters, plots, and motifs is identified and demonstrated.

Keywords: fairy tale, myth, fetishism, animism, totemism, giant, dragon, hero, divinity, legends, magic, mythical elements, primitive thinking.

Fairy tales have been moral, ethical, and educational gems in the oral tradition of people since ancient times, fulfilling their significant roles. From birth until death, people live with fairy tales. This presence is pronounced in some and subtle in others. Especially because our Uzbek people are known as a "child-loving" nation, our attitude towards fairy tales is well-developed. No one has heard at least one fairy tale in their childhood or hasn't shared the sweet memories of fairy tales with their children or conversed about fairy tales with their grandchildren. Every storyteller has images they specifically choose to present as heroes to every listener. There are many universally beloved fairy tale characters whose names are synonymous with evil. These images do not simply appear out of nowhere; their formation takes a long time. Likewise, in fairy tales, we encounter various magical, enchanted objects, animals, and plants, including mythological elements. Focusing on each of these images takes us back to the early stages of human thought development, namely into the realm of myths.

What are Myths? Mythology is the organized system of mythical concepts created by certain peoples, a collection of legends. Mythology is considered important in marking the initial stages of humanity's spiritual development. It has been studied as the foundation of understanding the universe, the initial stage of human artistic thinking. Myths, designed for oral storytelling, speaking, and narration, are included among examples of oral prose.

They typically present a certain short plot where magical reality predominates. As one of the artistic forms of folk prose, myths are also known as "legends." Mythological images have a unique and unparalleled place in every field of the art of language. Mainly, various appearances of mythical images are present in samples of folk oral creativity and also in our literary masterpieces. As human artistic thought gradually developed, mythology began to find its place in the fields of literature and art. In oral and written literary samples, such as epics, tales, legends, and fables, mythical images have grown. As a complete genre, myth has not fully survived in the system of narrative works belonging to oral creativity. Only in epics, fairy tales, legends, songs, riddles, ceremonial folklore, charms, and various beliefs do we find certain mythological plot elements. These remnants of myth, mythonyms, and mythologies serve as an important foundation for study. Over time, mythology has also begun to influence the works of creators. The most vivid images of mythology have deeply penetrated the very foundation of folk fairy tales. It is difficult to imagine nearly any fairy tale without myths. Because the essence of a myth is fabrication and fiction, it naturally shares a unique intrinsic connection with the fairy tale genre. Through the analysis of myth and fairy tale materials, the scope of meanings related to the mythological layer in fairy tales is unveiled.

In the interpretation of fairy tale heroes, plots, and motifs, the role of mythological concepts is clearly defined. To analyze the images in fairy tales, we must approach myths separately. Fairy tales are created for various themes and situations. Accordingly, scholars have classified types such as magical fairy tales, animal tales, everyday-life tales, and adventure tales. Often, we can encounter certain forms of myths in magical fairy tales. Beyond the images in fairy tales, each introductory style also has its unique connection to myths. Introductions like "Once upon a time," "In the ancient times," and "In the times of talking animals" are common. Elbek Jumanov, a postdoctoral researcher at the National University of Uzbekistan, states: "Returning to the beginning of fairy tales, it's notable that the indication of the events not being true in the introduction not only suggests the emergence of the fairy tale as a conscious artistic creation but also shows that it has evolved from the beginnings of ancient myths through a diffusion process. In short, epic beginnings have formed as a result of the diffusion process within the nature of ancient myths, securing a firm place in fairy tales as traditional formulas." Almost all our fairy tales are rich in myths. V. Propp was one of the first to scientifically study the influence of myth on fairy tales, stating, "Myth lives longer than customs and is reborn as fairy tales."

According to N. Roshin, "The fairy tale is a historical phenomenon, emerging when poetic fabric built on mythological imagination began to play a decisive role in thought."

One Uzbek fairy tale, "The Tale of the Three Hero Brothers," features a parrot that brings three pomegranates from faraway India to the king. Eating the pomegranate rejuvenates the consumer, preventing them from aging. Another famous Uzbek fairy tale, "Boil, Pot," features a pot with extraordinary properties. When placed on fire and commanded, "Boil, pot," it produces gold coins, continuing until the owner commands it to stop. In "Strike, Hammer," the hammer cries out against villains when instructed to do so. In "The Enchanted Boy," a boy lost in the forest and unable to find his way to the village comes across a magical spring, that transforms anyone who drinks its water into a deer. All these images are examples of fetishism. Tales about animals also reflect mythical views, such as people seeking divine power in animals, and expecting miracles from them, which is another aspect of mythical thinking. Various symbolic signs in fairy tales can also be considered examples of fetishism. For instance, the phoenix is a symbol of freedom, believed to exist only in free lands; and doves or swans, thought to bring peaceful life, are products of mythical thinking.

"The Mother Turned into a Bird" fairy tale, where a mother, distressed by her children's unkindness, transforms into a bird and flies to the distant sea, can serve as an example of anthropogenic myths, representing individuals with extraordinary qualities. From another perspective, this can also be seen as an example of totemism, as there's a magical connection between the human and the bird. In the tale "Tiny," a couple has a son as small as a thumb, who is eventually swallowed by a wolf. This depiction of a person in such a diminutive form also contains mythical elements. The story of "Earboy," about a child born with ears resembling those of an animal, like "Tiny," is a product of mythical thinking.

Myths are also classified into various types. As mentioned, anthropogenic myths about legendary characters with extraordinary traits—such as Hercules, Gilgamesh, Dorokoz, Ozitqi, Albasti, Alanqasar, Hubbi, Hizr, Luqman Hakim, Aristotle—are frequent in fairy tales and legends. The "Black-haired" fairy tale from the collection "Uzbek Folk Tales" features the lucky bird, an element of fetishism. Similar examples of fetishism include the magical staff, hat, and carpet in "Muqimomo," and the two flutes, magical sword, and wooden horse in "Sword Hero," showing miraculous properties. In "Mehrigiyo," the secret of the

mehrigiyo is that it always rescues its owner from various problematic situations. The magical power of inanimate objects is also significantly represented in this tale.

The image of the giant in "The Happy Bull," as well as the transformation of the chef and bull into various animals and objects through prayer, also reflects mythological perspectives. In "No'xatpolvon," a hero emerges from a tiny chickpea and sets off to save his sister and brothers from a giant, reviving his dead brothers with the water of life and death brought by a crow. The use of the water of life in the tale is a later fairy tale adaptation of the ancient mythology of the water of immortality from the Jamshid legend. The reviving water of life and death is an example of fetishism, while the revival of brothers through magical water represents animism. Thus, all mythological events in the fairy tale are harmoniously utilized. In "The Shepherd Boy and the Rich Man," the magical flute given to the shepherd boy by the wise old magician demonstrates belief in the magical power of inanimate objects, expecting miracles from them, which ties back to the concept of fetishism. The mythology of "Zariadr and Odatida," where Princess Odatida falls in love with Zariadr after seeing him in a dream, influenced many of our tales and epics that feature love stories beginning in dreams.

In "The Magic Cup," the tale discusses the unique property of a porcelain cup that multiplies into several cups with certain actions. This tale, too, is built on the belief in the magical power of inanimate objects, or fetishism. In the "The Old Man and the Giant" fairy tale, we encounter the image of a giant, and in "The Dragon," the image of a dragon. Some tales involving dragons and heroes, such as those about Gershasp, were created under the influence of myths and legends. The plot structure of these tales often mirrors that of myths: the hero defeats the dragon. Since mythology forms the basis of fairy tales, we can frequently encounter mythological elements in almost all fairy tales.

Relying on the opinions of scholarly researchers, it can be said that myths are the lifeblood of fairy tales. A fairy tale cannot exist without myths. These two always go hand in hand, complementing each other.

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